

seeking alternatives to floating rice culture. Instead of growing deep-water rice, farmers in some areas are beginning to plant a regular crop of rice immediately after the water has receded.

In Howrah, West Bengal, the group visited the first trial of new deep-water lines in a farmer's field. Lines are also being screened in Bihar. The Ford

Foundation supports these adaptive trials to accelerate the development and introduction of modern varieties in the deep-water areas where water levels vary and floods are common.

Observations of insect pests in deep-water rice fields (see photo) indicated the existence of an insect complex similar to that recorded in an in-depth survey in

Bangladesh that has been underway since February 1977. The most important pest was the yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas*. From stem borer counts conducted in the areas visited the mean percentage of infested stems in Burma was 5.3% (1 to 11% in 3 fields); in Thailand, 6% (0 to 14% in 6 fields); and in India, 9.3% (0 to 34% in 4 fields).

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Drought

Seedling drought test of deepwater rice in Thailand

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Sixty-two hybrid lines and traditional deep-water rice varieties were screened for drought tolerance at the seedling stage.

Listed in the table are hybrid lines that were tolerant to deep water and promising as seedlings under drought conditions.

Drought tolerance of deep-water rices at the seedling stage, Klong Luang Rice Experiment Station, Thailand.

Selection	Stress reading ^a	Recovery reading
BKN 7022-6-2	3.0	5.0
HTA 7203-5	3.0	6.0
BKN 6986-1-2	3.0	6.0
BKN 7022-6-4	3.0	6.0
BKN 6986-108-4	3.5	4.5
HTA 72044	3.5	5.0
HTA 7204-5	3.5	5.5
BKN 7022-10-1-2	4.0	5.0
BKN 6986-59-1	4.0	5.0
BKN 6986-59-7	4.0	5.0
BKN 7022-10-16	4.0	5.5
HTA 7204-2	4.0	5.5
BKN 6986-59-11	4.0	5.5
BKN 6986-66-2	4.5	5.0
BKN 6986-136-10	4.5	5.5
BKN 6986-136-16	4.5	5.5
BKN 6986-66-3	4.5	5.5
Leb Mue Nahng 111	4.5	6.1

^a Scale of 1-9 in Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

Pest management and control

DISEASES

Transmission of rice ragged stunt disease

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The occurrence of rice ragged stunt disease at IRRI led to the study of its transmission by mechanical means (rubbing and pin-prick method), through soil, and through seeds. None showed positive results.

Ragged stunt is transmitted by the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*. The brown planthoppers that were captured directly from diseased plants in the field and used to irrioculate rice seedlings caused some seedlings to develop symptoms of the disease.

The planthopper's ability to transmit the disease to a susceptible line, IR3839-1, was tested by daily serial transmission after acquisition feedings of 2, 3, 4, or more days until the death of the insect. The repeated tests involved 1,625 insects and 28,753 inoculated seedlings (1,906 seedlings died before symptoms developed). About 40% of the brown planthoppers transmitted the disease.

In a single test with a small number of insects, from 14 to 76% of the planthoppers were active transmitters. Both nymphs and adults transmitted the disease. No striking differences were observed in percentage of active transmitters between female and male adults (46 vs. 42%), and between the brachypterous and macropterous forms

(42 vs. 48%). After acquisition feedings of 2, 3, or 4 days, a few insects became immediately infective, while others became infective 33 days after feeding. The average latent period was 8.6 days. The insects retained infectivity after molting, indicating that the virus passage is transstadial. The highest rate of infection observed was that of 22 seedlings infected by one insect during its life span. About 33% of the infective insects infected only one seedling during their life span. The average was 4.3 infected seedlings/infective insect. The daily transmission pattern was generally intermittent. The retention period ranged from 3 to 35 days after acquisition feeding, averaging 14.6 days. The disease-transmitting days from the time that the insect became infective until its death varied from 3.2 to 100%, averaging 41.4%. As infective insects became old, they often failed to infect seedlings. The noninfective period immediately before an insect's death ranged from 0 to 30 days, averaging 7.0 days.

The transovarial passage was determined by the infectivity of the progeny of viruliferous insects. The progeny were obtained by rearing viruliferous insects on *Monochoria vaginalis*, which was assumed to be a nonhost of ragged stunt virus. The newly hatched nymphs were used to inoculate rice seedlings at daily intervals for 20 days, except when the insects died earlier. Of the 2,472 seedlings inoculated by 164 progeny of the viruliferous